

**METHODOLOGY OF TEACHING HOME APPLIANCE REPAIR TO STUDENTS
WITH MOBILITY IMPAIRMENTS**

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Abstract: This article is about the methods of education of students with disabilities in specialized vocational schools and how they will find their place in society in the future and acquire a well-rounded profession. Considered

Key words; Visual, household appliances, observation method, experiments, various visual aids, texts, operation of mechanisms, tools, illustration, demonstration method, practical method.

Visual methods can be used both to learn new material and to strengthen it. Learning how to repair household appliances is a way to form new knowledge and to apply knowledge in practice. The use of visual methods is especially important for children with traumatic brain injury due to their social and sometimes emotional deprivation. Using this method allows you to eliminate the negative effect of the derivative factor.

The method of observation is defined as the duration of the child's purposeful, systematic, changing perception of surrounding objects and events. It is often used to teach children the ability to notice changes in nature, plant life, animal behavior, observe people's work, analyze and generalize facts and events. Objects of observation are also arithmetic records, sets of objects, numbers, geometric figures, etc. In vocational schools, students observe experiments, various visual aids, texts, the operation of mechanisms, machines, etc. The active use of this method is explained by the creation of conditions that allow students to develop visual-figurative thinking, activate their attention, stimulate, expand and enrich their interest in learning based on sensory knowledge of the surrounding reality. The success of observations largely depends on the correct combination of the teacher's words and visual aids.

The main requirements for this method:

- clarity of the purpose of observation, comprehensibility for students;
- students' interest in conducting observations;
- conducting observation according to the developed plan, clearly dividing the general task of observation into stages;
- record observation results in records, graphs:
 - drawing conclusions based on the results of observation, discussing them and assessment. The main requirements for this method:
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Illustration - providing students with objects in a static state: reproductions, photographs, dolls, natural objects.

Each illustration should be clear, clearly related to the design and text, and should be as close as possible to the explanatory text.

Pictures are always combined with observation and verbal methods and explanations. They can accompany the oral presentation, thereby activating the students' knowledge activity; can be used to repeat and consolidate knowledge. But in some cases, they have independent value and have a research character. In such learning situations, students should independently draw conclusions and generalizations and defend them in the next lesson.

The main requirements for this method:

- careful selection of material (natural objects, models, layouts or images) and determination of the place and character of display (in a static state or in motion);
- the optimal number of exhibitions, taking into account the capabilities and needs of children with musculoskeletal disorders;
- it is very important to ensure the quality of illustrations and demonstrations, their reliability and safety measures in execution, as safety techniques are very important, because difficulties in movement, poor coordination and limited movements of hands can lead to accidents;
- conveying the purpose and content of demonstration to the minds of students;
- ensuring clarity and accuracy of perception;
- collective conclusion and independence of conclusions (when presenting new material).

Demonstration is showing students dynamic, developing, moving objects: experiments, films and videos, sound recordings, working mechanisms, machines, movement patterns, etc.

As visual aids, depending on the situation (teaching and educational task, availability of equipment, etc.), natural objects, three-dimensional visual aids (models, mock-ups), pictorial (pictures, reproductions), schematic (maps, schemes, diagrams), graphs) are used. benefits. When using them, you should follow the following basic rules:

- consideration of oculomotor disorders in children with musculoskeletal disorders;
- taking into account the lack of hand-eye coordination;
- timely provision of support for understanding;
- conducting the exhibition along with explanations, encouraging students' independent work by asking questions;
- use of aids for questioning and repetition;
- taking care of the aesthetic appearance of benefits; involving students in their production and repair;
- do not use many aids in the lesson, if necessary, divide them into 3-4 groups.

The special role and importance of sound, dynamic and audiovisual means is increasing. These are tape recordings, tapes and films, multimedia tools (interactive whiteboards, computer technologies). However, the use of film and filmstrips in more than 25% of the teaching time is considered ineffective. For audio tools, this time is even shorter, because children with musculoskeletal disorders cannot listen to a speech for more than 3-5 minutes without seeing the person speaking. Demonstration is showing students dynamic, developing, moving objects:

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- Students acquire knowledge, develop skills and competences by performing practical actions, influencing the studied object and changing it: exercise, laboratory work, practical work. In this case, the source of new knowledge and skills for students is the practical actions they perform.

Please note that practical methods in working with children with cerebral palsy are often ignored by teachers due to the difficulties of using them, especially when teaching children with manipulative functions. Although this is a big mistake. Preference should be given to these methods, because the quality and consistency of knowledge in children with cerebral palsy directly depends on practical activities related to the subject of their formation.

Practice is the repeated or repeated performance of a correct practical or mental action in order to master it or improve the quality of its performance. This method is of particular importance in elementary grades (for the formation of basic skills in writing, reading, performing calculation operations, working with tools and equipment in work classes, etc.).

Depending on the nature of the actions performed, there are exercises and creative exercises for specific (reproductive) reproduction, application of skills in an educational or real environment. During the lesson, students perform written and oral exercises. They can be done individually and frontally.

Before students perform an action, the teacher shows an example of its implementation and explains how to do it. Then the action is usually performed in a form that makes it easier to perceive (slowed down, isolated) with an explanation of each element. To check the understanding of the theoretical basis of the exercise, the teacher can ask the students and arrange for them to perform actions on the element. After that, he demonstrates the action again in a realistic form and organizes its implementation by students.

Simply performing or mechanically repeating a movement will not automatically improve it. During the exercises, skills improve and thinking develops under the following conditions:

- students' understanding of the theoretical basis of the exercise;
- conscious attention to skill improvement and improvement;
- step by step increasing the level of independence and strict consistency of the actions being performed;

-variety of exercises and their gradual complexity (exercising in different materials in different conditions);

- analyze the results of each exercise, understand the causes of errors and ways to eliminate them;

- correct distribution of exercises over time (not too often, so there is time to think and excessive fatigue does not appear, and not too little, so the skill is not forgotten);

- the content and form of organization of the training should be interesting for students, the training should be organized on the material of cognitive and educational value (use of games, making sure that the exercises will give practical useful results and hokozos).

Consolidation of practical knowledge is used to improve skills. They are very diverse and are used to teach various academic subjects to vocational school students. Depending on the educational goals, exercises are divided into training and inspection (control); at the place of work registration (classroom and home); according to the form of verbal expression of

thought (oral and written); according to the mental operations required of the student (analytical, analytical-synthetic, synthetic). There is also a classification according to the degree of independence. These are exercises in which the learned material is repeated; work on applying knowledge in new conditions; creative works. In addition, each subject has its own exercises based on its own characteristics.

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